

FEATURES OF PSYCHOLINGUISTIC DEVELOPMENT OF MEMORY IN CHILDREN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Annotation: *This article provides information on the features of psycholinguistic development of memory in children learning a foreign language in preschool education. It also discusses the types of memory skills a child has.*

Key words: *Visual memory, preschool childhood, mental state, verbal logical memory, pillar of ability, special movement, speech and thinking.*

The law "On Preschool Education and Upbringing" was signed on December 16, 2019 by our President. The law, signed by the President, defines the main directions of state policy in the field of preschool education and upbringing. In particular, the state guarantees the right of every child to undergo one year of compulsory one-year preparation for general secondary education in public preschools one year before enrollment in general secondary education. By law, a preschool organization can be a government organization. Preschool education organizations are organized in the following types:

- general type preschool education organization
- a multidisciplinary specialized preschool education organization
- preschool education organization with inclusive groups
- a joint-type preschool organization

Taking advantage of these opportunities, I think we need to effectively implement education based on the mental activity of the child. Memory is one of the types of mental activity designed to store, collect and reproduce information. The ability to use information in the field of mind to organize information about the body's reactions over a long period of time and to organize subsequent work. Memory is the basis of human ability, the condition of learning to acquire knowledge, the formation of skills. Without memory, neither man nor society can hold on normally. Because of the perfection of his memory, man was separated from the animal kingdom and he reached the heights he now possesses. It is unimaginable that humanity will develop further without constantly improving this function. Preschool is a period of rapid development of mental processes, which allows the child to get acquainted with the reality around him. Natural memory

capabilities appear to a large extent in preschool age. In preschool, memory is superior to other abilities in the rate of development, the child learns to draw, sees an unusual object and begins to think about the burdens of life. Preschool children remember verses, counters, riddles, fairy tales is explained by the rapid development. The child attracts everything bright, beautiful, unusual attention. The child remembers involuntarily. Observations of children's mental development and special studies show that a child's memory develops with age and changes in size and quality. Memory development is reflected in different stages of a child's life. An important moment in development of the memory of a great preschooler is the perception of personal memories. They reflect important events in the child's life, successes in his or her activities and relationships with adults with peers. An older child develops verbal logical memory at a preschool age. A 6-7 year old child can easily use this word to memories semantic connections, sets. All of which contribute to an increase in the volume of memorized material.

Visual memory is related to the storage and reproduction of visual images.

Hearing memory is the ability to memorize and repeat these different sounds well: music, speech.

Intuitive memory is concerned with remembering by holding and touching these different things.

Visual uses visual objects such as graphs, charts, pictures. It learns better in lessons by watching them mentally pictures situations and problems. It tends remember things that are written down.

Auditory-retains information through hearing and speaking. It often prefers to be told how to do things. It summarizes key ideas out loud help memorization. It often has musical talents Kinesthetic-likes a "hands-on" approach to learn new material. Kinesthetic or tactile learners are always touching things and learn best by doing. Kinesthetic learners are constantly moving about and want to be touching the object they are learning from. In meeting settings, kinesthetic learners may stand out because of their need to move.

D.B.Elkonin found that 3-year-olds were able to identify a goal they needed to remember at the request of an adult and that a 4-year-old could independently identify the same goal. The presence of memory and the purpose of recollection is often observed only in children of preschool age. Preschoolers mainly resort to memorization methods, mainly at the age of 6-7 years. Attempts to form mental logical connections between the words they remember are distinguished. This is confirmed by the nature of reproduction: the child changes the order of the things given to him during reproduction and combines them according to purpose. Additional visual images begin to appear in memory. Logical methods of memorizing E.O.Smirnova include grouping materials based first on the temporal or spatial proximity of the memorized material elements and then on the semantic proximity. We can also use a variety of didactic games to enhance children's

memory. For example, application games with mosaics. In these games, it is easy to change the places of the pictures, to combine them into different situations, so that additional speech situations help the children to develop their speech. Lexical tables for speech development are now used in schools and preschools. In addition to sound materials, lexical tables can also use visual materials in the form of humorous, humorously executed pictures. Pictures serve as commentary and motivating functions. In conclusion, it can be said that a child's memory, that is, his memory, changes over the years. Therefore, I believe that we need to show and teach our children from an early age the events and situations that are full of good thoughts and ideas.

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